

Model of Rationale for Code Commits

Component	Question	Example Answer
Goal	<i>What do you want to achieve?</i>	<i>I want to modify our usage of try/catch blocks in a way that they all account for unexpected exceptions</i>
Need	<i>Why do you need to achieve that?</i>	<i>A new company directive requires that all our try/catch block statements include the Exception case by June 1st.</i>
Location	<i>What artifacts were changed?</i>	<i>I made changes in every catch/block that I could find in the core branch.</i>
Modifications	<i>What specific changes were performed in the artifacts?</i>	<i>I added an "Exception (e)" case to all of them and handled it by logging a general exception message.</i>
Alternatives	<i>What other alternatives did you have?</i>	<i>Spend the time to consider the best way to handle Exception for each instance of a try/catch block</i>
Selected alternative	<i>Why did you make those specific changes and not others?</i>	<i>A general exception message works for now. It was more efficient to apply the same implementation to all locations.</i>
Validation	<i>How do those specific changes achieve the goal?</i>	<i>This partially achieved our goal, because we may be able to handle some of these exceptions in a more specific way.</i>
Benefits	<i>What is the benefit of what you want to achieve?</i>	<i>This will increase the quality of our system by now having decided how to handle exceptions that we did not think about before.</i>
Costs	<i>What risks could come from these changes?</i>	<i>Some test cases may now fail because of the new exception messages in the logs.</i>